

A Nexus Between Employee Work Engagement and Sustainable Employability

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Abstract : Purpose The study aimed to gain an improved knowledge of the relation between psychological empowerment, well-being, and sustained employment. Besides, the research model is mediated through employee work engagement to achieve sustainable employability. Design/Methodology/Approach To empirically test the research model, employees from automotive industry in Chennai were chosen as respondents, and a survey was executed among them, with possible data acquired from 397 respondents. The aim of the present research was to ascertain the impact of psychological well-being, psychological empowerment and job creation on attaining long-term work employability through employee work engagement. Findings The study revealed that psychological well-being, psychological empowerment, job crafting and employee work engagement exhibits a close association on sustainable employability. Job crafting being the most positive significance influence on Employable sustainability. Practical Implication: Job crafting enables workers to diversify their palette of abilities, making them more versatile to changes in the workplace. By engaging in relational crafting, employees can improve their interactions with colleagues, leading to a more supportive and collaborative work environment. Originality / Value: The results obtained in the study would lay as a base for the future researchers. Further the management can consider the results and incorporate accordingly to implement in the organisation as policies and strategies.

Keywords: Psychological well-being (PWB), psychological empowerment (PE), Job Crafting (JC), Employee work Engagement (EWE), Sustainable employability (SE)

Introduction

Employee work engagement is a burgeoning notion among the business scenario Hai et al., (2020). According to Fleuren et al. (2018), workplace employee engagement improves organisational effectiveness. It was a clean decline in workplace productivity as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic's significant impact on employees' psychological welfare Dirani et al., (2020). Thus, among practitioners, considering employee engagement at work has emerged as a key business agenda area EWE towards work, dedication, a work-related attitude, and the

ability to persevere through tasks at work are all considered components of employee job engagement. Accordingly, a situation where an individual has job security during a crisis and keeps working despite outside threats is referred to as sustainable employability Rahi, (2022b). Further, it has been noted by Kersemaekers et al., (2018) that there is quite a lot of potential to explore aspects like employee psychological behaviour, including empowerment and well-being, in an EWE context. In order to address this research gap, the current study creates an integrated research model that examines employee behaviour with regard to work engagement and sustainable employability by fusing job crafting techniques with psychological aspects.

Psychological factors have been demonstrated to have a lasting impact on employee behavior and encourage them to remain with the company 'Pathak & Srivastava, (2020). Additionally, it's been observed that psychological health promotes creativity and satisfaction with work Grant et al., (2007). In order to understand, Robertson and Cooper (2010) have outlined employee psychological well-being and psychological empowerment in the research model to explain how these psychological dimensions influence employee behavior towards employee work engagement (EWE) and contribute to sustainable employability. With support from earlier studies by Koroglu and Ozmen (2021). Determining how job crafting affects long-term employability is another topic of research that requires the researcher's consideration. By modifying job limitations or making the most of their job needs and resources, job crafting enables people to adapt to their work environment Wrzesniewski and Dutton, (2001); Tims et al., (2022). According to research, job crafting enhances centralised work (re)design techniques and has several advantages for both individuals and organisations Akkermans & Tims, (2017); Tims et al., (2013). Aside from the potential advantages of job crafting for people and organisations, research on its causes, effects, and boundary conditions is still in its early stages Kim et al., (2018); Rogala and Cieslak, (2020); Rudolph et al., (2017); Wang et al., (2020). First, when it comes to antecedents, researchers mostly examine why people build their careers Wang et al., (2020); however, it is yet unknown how organisations and employers support job crafting. Seldom have studies on the links between job crafting and sustainable employability been conducted Irfan and Qadeer, (2020); Kaiser, (2021); Le Blanc et al., (2020). Therefore, organisations are examining the role that work design plays in boosting long-term employability Kaiser, (2021). The present study clarifies the elements that affect EWE at work and long-term employment, with job design, psychological empowerment, and psychological well-being serving as significant contributors to both. In this study the link between the predictor and criteria variables is established.

Research Background and Hypotheses Development

Psychological well-being

According to Ryff (1989), PWB comprises both a theory and a measurement. It may be examined through fundamental elements including ownership and autonomy, having a purpose in existence, growing personally, and having meaningful relationships with others. PWB was examined as a personal resource in Xanthopoulou et al.'s (2021) study, and the hypothesis was that employees perform significantly better and feel more capable of influencing their

environment when they are in a better psychological state at work Schaufeli, (2020). According to Van Dam et al., (2017), psychological variables have significant impacts on long-term employability. Thus, freedom, knowledge, significance, and a strong sense of commitment among employees towards management procedures are characteristics of psychological empowerment Jena et al., (2018); Pathak and Srivastava, (2020). The topics of psychological empowerment and well-being among employees have drawn interest from researchers and professionals Van De Voorde et al., (2022), Guest, (2017), Grant et al., (2007). As we move forward, workers who have experienced psychological empowerment have demonstrated a high level of willingness to accomplish tasks Pathak and Srivastava, (2020); Salehi et al., (2020). The following theories are therefore put forth and supported by previously published studies by Grant et al. (2007), Spreitzer (2008) Grant et al., 2007;

H₁: Psychological well-being has a favourable impact on sustainable employability.

Psychological empowerment

Four cognitive states—meaning, competence, self-determination, and impact—have been identified as psychological states that exhibit psychological empowerment. Psychological empowerment, is the degree to which workers feel they can influence their position and how they view themselves in the workplace. Feeling optimistic and enthusiastic about their work, psychologically empowered individuals believe they have their own responsibilities and influence inside an organization. Meaning is an understanding that one's labour is significant and meaningful, according to Spreitzer. The belief in one's own ability to perform tasks successfully, or self-efficacy, is shown by competence. The belief that one can have an influence on the results of their job is referred to as impact. The self-determination is the sense of independence that an individual has, namely, the capacity to decide how to begin and conclude tasks.

Autonomy, knowledge, significance, and a strong sense of commitment from employees towards management procedures are characteristics of psychological empowerment Pathak and Srivastava, (2020). As we move forward, workers who have experienced psychological empowerment have demonstrated a high level of willingness to finish tasks Thus, we suggest:

H₂: Psychological empowerment has a significant positive impact on sustainable employability.

Job crafting

According to Le Blanc et al. (2017), job crafting is an ongoing process that supports long-term employability in two ways. In the beginning, it enables everyone to redesign tasks in a way that best suits their needs. According to Bakker and Demerouti (2018), it also creates a positive cycle of job and personal resources and empowers people to affect their work environment. People can remain proactive, engaged, and adaptable at work with the support of this resource gain cycle. Apart from helping an employee fulfil the criteria of their present position, job crafting promotes a learning environment that helps them advance professionally and personally. Achieving desired work outcomes that partially align with employability is possible

through job crafting Tims et al., (2012). The ability and desire of workers to work till retirement are positively correlated with job crafting Vanbelle et al., (2017). These conclusions are corroborated by a few recent research. Examples of how job crafting enhances perceived employability are provided by Akkermans and Tims (2017). More resources are available to those who exhibit broad job crafting behaviours, enabling them to create better career plans and achieve their professional goals. Job crafting influences permanent employees perceived external employability in a positive way, according to Plomp et al., (2019). Consequently, the probability of long-term employability is enhanced by job crafting. After summarising the main points of the discussion, the following hypothesis is put forth in light of the likelihood that job crafting will increase workers' total sustainable employability:

H₃: Job crafting has a significant impact on sustainable employability.

Employee work engagement as mediator

As per Zhang et al. (2013), EWE is the degree to which workers exhibit favourable attitudes towards their work and exhibit complete commitment and focus. According to several studies by Jaramillo et al., (2005) and Peng et al., (2022), raised employee work engagement and promoted organisational productivity. The degree to which an emotional connection is strengthened between an employee and the organisation is defined in the literature as effective commitment Hussain et al., (2020); Salehi et al., (2021); Teo et al., (2020). Effective job engagement, according to Zhang et al. (2013), is a crucial aspect of employee well-being and has a favourable effect on worker output. Teo et al. (2020) hypothesised in a recent study that affective commitment is a result of work engagement for workers. Current study, however, addons by examining the moderating role that employee work engagement plays in the relationships between psychological health, job crafting, empowerment, and employability over the long run. Research by Fu and Deshpande, (2014); Jaramillo et al., (2005); Peng et al., (2016) has verified that affective employee commitment contributed to employees' loyalty to an organisation and improved their sustainable employability. Consequently, it is hypothesised that: employability, and consequently, it is suggested that:

H₄: PWB has a significant positive impact on EWE.

H₅: PE has an impact on EWE.

H₆: Job crafting has positive impact on EWE.

Sustainable Employability

According to Fleuren et al. (2016), sustainable employability refers to a worker's capacity to continue working throughout the duration of their career. Still, this notion has to be improved Fleuren et al., (2016) because it is fragmented, complex, and ambiguous due to different conceptualisations Van Harten, (2016). According to De Cuyper et al. (2012), indicates that "ability to continue working" or "motivation to continue working" are key components of the idea of sustainable employability. Work engagement, employability, workability, health, and vitality are the metrics used to quantify the ability to continue working. According to Van

Harten (2016), workability and engagement elements are connected concepts that are related to well-being, it implies that these two factors must be the results of sustainable employment. Different definitions of employability take sustainability into account. Employability is a more general term. Van Vuuren et al. (2011) define employability as the "willingness and ability" of an individual to do work activities consistently. As to Van der Heijden (2012), there is a positive correlation between an employee's perceived employability and their likelihood of being able to continue working. In other words, the person's "ability to continue working" is adequately addressed by their perceived employability. From the explanation above, we may suggest that the fundamental elements of "continue working" are "ability and motivation." As to Irfan and Qadeer (2020, p. 127), sustainable employability refers to the degree of an employee's capacity and motivation to work successfully both now and in the future.

H7: EWE has an impact on SE.

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Prepared by Authors (2024)

Research Gap

The relationship between job crafting and sustainable employability remains underexplored, particularly in developing countries such as India. While job crafting—a process where employees proactively modify their job roles to enhance personal meaning and engagement—has been extensively studied in developed nations, its connection to sustainable employability in India’s automotive industry requires further investigation. Previous research has highlighted the role of psychological well-being and psychological empowerment in shaping employee behavior and performance, but the integration of job crafting as a mediating or moderating factor remains insufficiently explored. Job crafting may play a pivotal role in helping employees adapt to changing job demands, thereby fostering sustainable employability by improving long-term job satisfaction, adaptability, and engagement.

Moreover, replicating the research model in India, a developing nation, offers a unique opportunity to understand how social and economic factors impact these relationships. India’s automotive industry is rapidly evolving, presenting both challenges and opportunities for

workforce sustainability. Examining how job crafting interacts with psychological well-being and empowerment in this context can shed light on the social and economic gaps influencing sustainable employability. Such research could provide valuable insights for policymakers and HR practitioners, enabling them to implement strategies that promote long-term employee performance and retention in the competitive, fast-changing environment of the automotive sector.

Research Objectives

- To ascertain the relationship of psychological well-being, psychological empowerment and job crafting on sustainable employability.
- To intervene the mediating role of employee work engagement in achieving sustainable employability.
- To examine the interaction between employee work engagement and sustainable employability.

Research Methodology

Sampling design and Data collection

Purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling procedure, is implemented in the investigation. This procedure includes the selection of participants who are instantly available and ready to participate in the survey. When time or resources are scarce, convenience sampling is frequently implemented; however, it may restrict the generalisation of the results. The study will continue an ongoing study in the automobile sector which employed 349 out of 374 samples; selecting a proper method of sampling proves the relevance by ensuring the validity and reliability of the study. The research focuses on employees working in private sector organizations. The automotive industry in India is specifically mentioned, but the sampling strategy may apply to various private sectors based on the study's scope. Several methods are applicable with 349 samples using the statistical software packages SPSS and SMART-PLS, as determined by the study purpose. Using a Likert scale and multiple-choice questions ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree," the data is gathered through surveys. 66 samples were used in the pilot run to confirm the survey instrument was reliable.

Measures

Psychological well-being: The Psychological Well-Being Scales (PWB) established by Ryff, (1989) are among the most well-known instruments for measuring PWB. This scale, which has been widely utilised in psychological research, assesses the six previously stated dimensions. A Likert scale is usually used to measure respondents' agreement or disagreement with a set of 6 items where, 1 represents strongly disagree, while 5 indicates strongly agree.

Psychological empowerment: Spreitzer, (1995) developed the Psychological Empowerment Scale, which is the popular instruments to measure psychological empowerment. In order

determine employees' psychological empowerment, organisations commonly use this scale, which evaluates the eight items.

Job Crafting: The Job Crafting Scale, developed by Tims et al., (2012), is often used indicator of job crafting. Employee participation in the three aspects of job crafting is measured by this scale using 3 items.

Employee work Engagement: One of the most widely used tools for assessing work engagement is the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES). The UWES, created by Schaufeli et al. (2002), evaluates vigour, devotion, and absorption—the three aspects of work engagement representing 6 items.

Sustainable employability: However, in the present study, items were grabbed from an existent scale and evaluated from prior studies. Spreitzer (1995) formulated tool for psychological well-being. Finally, construct items for outcome variables such as employee work engagement and long-term employability were adopted from earlier studies by Fleuren et al. (2018). The demographic characteristics were examined using a nominal and ordinal scales.

Analysis

Construct reliability and validity

In order to assess the validity and reliability of the model, psychological well-being and sustainable employability are the constructs, when it comes to psychological well-being, Cronbach's Alpha is 0.709. Sustainable Employability prospects in the long run as 0.810 and shows relatively a good internal consistency indicated by the fact that both constructs achieve this level. Reliability Composite (ρ_a and ρ_c): Positive well-being was $\rho_a = 0.907$ and $\rho_c = 0.747$ shows its role stability. The fact that both constructs are higher than this indicates that they are accurately measured. The psychological well-being variable has an average extracted variance (AVE) of 0.472. Achieving long-term employment: 0.578 When the AVE is more than 0.5, it means that the construct typically accounts for over 50% of the variation in its indicators. But psychological well-being's AVE of 0.472 is just below the cutoff, so it's possible that this concept doesn't explain nearly enough variation in its indicators. Both the psychological well-being and the sustainable employability constructs demonstrate high levels of dependability, with Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability scores all exceeding the acceptable threshold of 0.7. The reliability metrics are sturdy, but the construct does not explain enough variation in its indicators (AVE = 0.472), which might mean that there are concerns with convergent validity. The concept explains a sufficient amount of variance in its indicators, indicating sustainable employability. Reliability and validity are good, with an AVE over the 0.5 threshold. Ultimately, although both constructs show impressive dependability, the psychological well-being construct might use some further work to boost its convergent validity.

Demographic profile and Characteristics

Table no 1: Demographic profile and Characteristics

S.No	Demography variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Male	198	57
		Female	151	43
		Total	349	100
2	Age	25-30	117	34
		30-35	75	21
		35-40	58	17
		40-45	57	16
		45-50	26	7
		50 and above	16	5
		Total	349	100
3	Marital status	Married	214	61
		Unmarried	135	39
		Total	349	100
4	Level of Education	Diploma	34	10
		Graduation-UG	178	51
		Graduation-PG	86	24
		External Certification	51	15
		Total	349	100
5	Work Experience	Fresher	156	45
		1-5 Years	79	23
		5-10 Years	58	17
		10-15 Years	37	10
		More Than 15 Years	19	5
		Total	349	100
6	Job classification	Entry	178	51
		Intermediate	79	23
		Experienced	51	14
		Specialist	24	7
		Expert	17	5
		Total	349	100
7	Income Level	< 3 lakhs	154	44
		3.01- 4 lakhs	88	25
		4.01-5 Lakhs	69	20
		>5 lakhs	38	11
		Total	349	100

Source: Prepared by Authors (2024)

This table presents a demographic representation of the sample population, highlighting the distribution across several key variables such as gender, age, marital status, education, work experience, job classification, and income level. An analysis of the data is provided below:

Gender: of the 349 respondents in the sample, men (57%) represent slightly more of the respondents than women (43%). Age: The age range is broad; with the greatest proportion of the group being between 25 and 30 years old (34%). The age groups of 35–40 (17%) and 30–35 (21%), after that, come next. 50 and older (5%), and 45–50% are the two age groups with the lowest percentages. Marital Status: 39% of respondents are single, while 61% of respondents are married. Education Level: 51% of the population has a graduate degree (UG), with the majority having undergraduate degrees. The percentage of people with postgraduate degrees (PG) is 24%; people with diplomas (10%) and external certificates (15%) are next in line.

Work Experience: Of the sample, 45% are recent graduates, representing a significant portion. 23% of respondents have one to five years of experience, whereas 17% have five to ten years. Merely 10% of the responders have 10 to 15 years of experience, and only 5% have more than fifteen years. Job Classification: Of the respondents, 51% are classified as entry-level employees. Of these, 23% belong to the intermediate level and 14% to the experienced category. Expert and specialist levels are under-represented, at 5% and 7%, respectively. Income Level: 14 percent of the respondents earn less than three lakhs a year. Twenty percent make between 4.01 and 5 lakhs, while 25% make between 3.01 and 4 lakhs. Eleven percent of the sample earns more than five lakhs. The sample population is mainly made up of younger people (25–30 years old), most of them are male, and a sizable percentage of them are recent graduates. With an undergraduate degree, the majority of responders are married and work in entry-level roles. The bulk of respondents appear to be in the lower to middle income ranges based on the income distribution.

Correlation

The result presented with the Pearson correlation are to observe the relationship among the variables and the findings reveal that the Pearson correlation coefficient and its significance value with the sample size of 349. It is ought to find that the correlation coefficient $r = 0.918$ which stand as a strong positive correlation with sustainable employability and job crafting they are also found to be statistically significant ($p=0.005$). Further the correlation coefficient of psychological empowerment and sustainable employability stands to be the second strong positive relationship between the variables and proves to be statistically significant with r value as 0.900. The relationship between the EWE which stand as the mediating variable and finds a strong positive relationship with PE with the r value as 0.868 Also the correlation coefficient $r = 0.868$ for PWB and the psychological empowerment and exhibits a strong positive relationship between the variables. Further the relationship between psychological wellbeing and the sustainable employability found to be positive with coefficient of r value as 0.854. Finally the least but still exhibits the positive relationship between JC and PWB between job crafting and psychological empowerment with its r value as 0.743 and 0.759.

Regression

Regression analysis gives the overview of the study as the hypothesis studies the relationship between psychological well-being and the sustainable employability. To interpret on the

analysis R value is found to be 0.854 which explains high degree of correlation. As the R^2 indicates the how far the total variation of the sustainable employability is explained by psychological well-being as it stands to be 73% as R square value. Durbin Watson value is found to be 2.037 exhibits a positive autocorrelation. ANOVA in regression explains how far the model fits the data which indicates the statistical significance predicts the sustainable employability the regression model thus ensures the hypothesis, H_1 is accepted. The coefficient provides with the required information to predict psychological well-being contributing to sustainable employability.

Table no 2: R Square

Hypothesis	R Square
H₁ : Psychological well-being – sustainable employability	73%
H₃ : Psychological Empowerment - sustainable employability	81%
H₅ : Job Crafting - sustainable employability	84%
H₇ : Employee work engagement - Sustainable employability	73%

Source: Prepared by Authors (2024)

Further H_3 was tested by regression analysis interpret between psychological empowerment on sustainable employability and found R value to be 0.900 which explains high degree of correlation between the variables. As the R^2 indicates the how far the total variation of the sustainable employability is explained by psychological well-being as it stands to be 81% as R square value. Durbin Watson found to be 1.794 exhibits a positive autocorrelation. ANOVA in regression explains how far the model fits the data which indicates the statistical significance predicts the sustainable employability the regression model thus ensures the hypothesis, H_1 is accepted. The coefficient provides with the required information to predict psychological empowerment supports sustainable employability.

Job crafting is tested with sustainable employability using regression analysis as the study demands the hypothesis the relationship and to interpret the output with the R value as 0.918 which explains high degree of correlation. As the R^2 represents the how far the total variation of the sustainable employability is explained by psychological well-being as it stands to be 84 % as R square value. Durbin Watson value is found to be 2.290 exhibits a positive autocorrelation. ANOVA in regression explains how far the model fits the data which indicates the statistical significance predicts the sustainable employability the regression model thus ensures the hypothesis, H_5 is accepted. The coefficient provides with the required information to predict job crafting and supports to sustainable employability.

H_7 hypothesis explains, as the study confronts the relationship between EWE and SE. To interpret on analysis R value is found to be 0.854 which explains high degree of correlation. As the R^2 indicates the how far the total variation of the sustainable employability is explained by employee work engagement as it stands to be 73% as R square value. Durbin Watson value

is found to be 2.037 exhibits a positive autocorrelation. ANOVA in regression explains how far the model fits the data which indicates the statistical significance predicts the sustainable employability the regression model thus ensures the hypothesis, H₇ is accepted. The coefficient provides with the required information to predict employee contributing to sustainable employability.

Descriptive Statistics

Table No 3 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Analysis N
PWB 1	4.18	.528	349
PWB 2	4.21	.465	349
PWB 3	4.31	.499	349
PWB 4	4.44	.497	349
PWB 5	4.44	.497	349
PWB 6	4.24	.430	349
PE 1	4.16	.653	349
PE 2	4.14	.628	349
PE 3	4.25	.454	349
PE 4	4.26	.436	349
PE 5	4.36	.487	349
PE 6	4.20	.424	349
PE 7	4.20	.424	349
PE 8	4.20	.424	349
JC 1	4.15	.549	349
JC 2	4.17	.410	349
JC 3	4.22	.450	349
JC 4	4.19	.436	349
EWE 1	4.25	.454	349
EWE 2	4.20	.424	349
EWE 3	4.36	.487	349
EWE 4	4.20	.424	349
EWE 5	4.44	.497	349
EWE 6	4.19	.397	349
SE 1	3.97	.964	349
SE 2	4.20	.424	349
SE 3	4.19	.447	349
SE 4	4.19	.397	349
SE 5	4.19	.397	349
SE 6	4.44	.497	349

Source: Prepared by Authors (2024)

The table displays descriptive data for a range of psychological and job-related characteristics that were measured across 349 participants. These constructs include Psychological Empowerment, Job Crafting, Psychological Well-Being, and Sustainable Employability. A multiple-item assessment is conducted for each component, with the mean

and standard deviation of each item provided. The elements related to Psychological Well-Being have mean values ranging from 4.18 to 4.44. The mean scores for Items 4 and 5 are the highest (4.44), indicating that individuals feel generally good about these elements of their well-being. Because of the low standard deviations (which range from .430 to .528), it can be seen that respondents' answers are consistently distributed around the mean, which is indicative of consistency in their well-being. The questions related to Psychological Empowerment have mean values ranging from 4.14 to 4.36. With the highest mean score of 4.36 for item 5, there is a strong sense of empowerment in this domain. Item 1 has the most differences among the standard deviations, which range from .424 to .653, indicating that participants' perceptions of this component of empowerment varied. Job Crafting products have mean scores ranging from 4.15 to 4.22. With item 3's highest mean score of 4.22, participants appear to engage in job crafting behaviours to a good degree. The comparatively low standard deviations (from .410 to .549) suggest that individuals' responses were consistent. The factors related to Sustainable Employability have mean scores ranging from 3.97 to 4.20. With the lowest mean score (3.97) for item 1, there may be a difference in respondents' perceptions of their long-term employability in this area. With Item 1 exhibiting the most variability and corresponding disparities in participant responses, the standard deviations range from .397 to .964. The majority of the items have high average values, which suggests that the respondents generally have positive perceptions of their psychological well-being, empowerment, ability to choose their jobs, and long-term employability. With the exception of a few items that exhibit greater variability, the standard deviations of the majority of the items indicate that respondents' answers are consistent.

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

Table No 4 Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of	Cumulative	Total	% of	Cumulative	Total	% of	Cumulative
		Variance	%		Variance	%		Variance	%
1	15.122	65.750	65.750	15.122	65.750	65.750	9.656	41.981	41.981
2	2.052	8.921	74.671	2.052	8.921	74.671	3.836	16.677	58.658
3	1.089	4.735	79.405	1.089	4.735	79.405	2.956	12.853	71.511
4	1.001	4.351	83.756	1.001	4.351	83.756	2.816	12.245	83.756
5	0.759	3.300	87.056						
6	0.662	2.878	89.934						
7	0.435	1.891	91.825						
8	0.404	1.756	93.581						
9	0.353	1.534	95.115						
10	0.280	1.218	96.333						
11	0.244	1.060	97.393						
12	0.176	0.763	98.156						
13	0.120	0.523	98.679						
14	0.097	0.420	99.098						
15	0.069	0.301	99.400						
16	0.051	0.222	99.621						
17	0.027	0.115	99.737						
18	0.025	0.109	99.846						
19	0.020	0.089	99.935						

20	0.015	0.065	100.000
21	3.880E-16	1.687E-15	100.000
22	1.247E-16	5.423E-16	100.000
23	-7.055E-17	-3.067E-16	100.000

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Source: Prepared by Authors (2024)

The results of a Principal Component Analysis (PCA), a statistical method used to decrease a dataset's dimensionality while preserving as much variability as feasible, are displayed in this table. The table illustrates the contribution of every significant factor to the total variance in the data. Component 1 comprises 65.750% of the total variance and has an eigenvalue of 15.122. Component 2 contributes 8.921% of the total variance and has an eigenvalue of 2.052. Component 3 has an eigenvalue of 1.089 and contributes 4.735% of the total variance. 4.351% of the variation is explained by component 4, which has an eigenvalue of 1.001. With eigenvalues smaller than 1, the following components are less effective at explaining variation. Overall variation is explained by the first four components collectively in 83.756% of cases. According to this, the most important patterns in the data are represented by these four elements. Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings. This indicates that the first four components account for 83.756% of the total variance after extraction, as these values match the Initial Eigenvalues. After rotation, Component 1 now accounts for 41.981% of the variation. 16.677% of the variance is explained by component 2. 12.853% of the variance is explained by component 3. 12.245% of the variation is explained by component 4. Because of the rotation's greater distribution of variation among these components, it is now simpler to understand each one individually. Using PCA, the original dataset was reduced to four significant components, which together account for 83.756% of the variation. The variance is distributed more fairly among the first four components, each of which represents a distinct aspect of the data, following rotation. The first four components, or components with eigenvalues larger than 1, are usually kept for additional analysis since they account for a larger portion of the variation than any one original variable could. The data is made easier to understand and utilize in subsequent solving or decision-making processes by this analysis, which helps to simplify the data while preserving the majority of its variability.

Rotated Component matrix

Table no 5 Rotated Component matrix

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
PWB 1	0.729	0.398	0.172	
PWB 2	0.690	0.333	0.170	0.408
PWB 3	0.626	0.120	0.301	0.397
PWB 4	0.223	0.257	0.915	0.126
PWB 5	0.223	0.257	0.915	0.126
PWB 6	0.410	0.786	0.244	0.224
PE 1	0.281	0.207		0.909

PE 2	0.401	0.169	0.256	0.774
PE 3	0.467	0.642	0.429	0.202
PE 4	0.453	0.715	0.354	0.174
PE 5	0.253	0.669	0.358	0.315
PE 6	0.821	0.219	0.292	0.251
PE 7	0.821	0.219	0.292	0.251
PE 8	0.672	0.429		0.365
JC 1	0.676	0.358	0.176	
JC 2	0.751	0.419	0.114	0.301
JC 3	0.808	0.325	0.151	0.253
JC 4	0.788	0.281	0.261	0.278
EWE 1	0.848	0.289	0.204	0.269
EWE 2	0.530	0.624	0.174	0.320
EWE 3	0.789	0.486	0.326	0.319
EWE 4	0.784	0.305		0.480
EWE 5	0.675	0.563	0.936	0.261
EWE 6	0.582	0.590	0.282	0.272
SE 1	0.783	0.494	0.178	0.185
SE 2	0.765	0.265	0.209	0.280
SE 3	0.759	0.320	0.127	0.308
SE 4	0.835	0.295	0.316	0.236
SE 5	0.835	0.295	0.316	0.236
SE 6	0.818	0.326	0.151	0.253

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.^a

a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.

Source: Prepared by Authors (2024)

Based on a Principal Component Analysis (PCA), this table represents the components matrix. Through the establishment of new dimensions known as principal components, a statistical technique known as principal component analysis (PCA) can reduce the dimensionality of a dataset. According to how much deviation from the original data they can explain, these uncorrelated main components are ranked in order. Every individual cell within the matrix signifies the loading (correlation) of every initial variable with one of the four primary components. The association between the variable and the component is stronger when the absolute values are higher. While loadings near 0 signify little to no correlation, loadings near 1 or -1 suggest that the component and the variable are significantly connected.

Component 1: The highest loadings are seen in items 1, 2, 3, and 6 related to Psychological Well-being. The loadings for items 6 and 7 are substantial in Psychological Empowerment. Items 1, 2, 3, and 4 have significant loadings in the job crafting process. Items 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 have high loadings in terms of sustainable employability. In terms of psychological well-being, empowerment, job crafting, and sustainable employability, this component is representative of a broad dimension. *Component 2:* There is a strong loading on item 6 on Psychological Well-being. Items 3, 4, and 5 have significant loadings in relation to psychological empowerment.

This element may especially stand for elements of psychological well-being and empowerment. *Component 3:* Items 4 and 5 have extremely high loadings in relation to psychological well-being. The elements related to psychological well-being appear to be specifically correlated with this component. *Component 4:* The items with the highest loadings in Component 4, Psychological Empowerment, are 1 and 2. There appears to be another unique facet of psychological empowerment represented by this component.

Fig no 2 PLS-SEM Model

Source: Prepared by Authors (2024)

EWE in their job as a result of their psychological well-being where the path coefficient is found to be 0.047 seems to be impacting employees' psychological well-being on their engagement at work is minimal. This suggests that there is a weak correlation between worker involvement and improvements in psychological well-being. Psychological empowerment leads to 0.414 whose levels of employee work engagement is moderately good effect of psychological empowerment in the workplace. Work engagement rises in tandem with psychological empowerment, according to the research result. Employee work engagement grew to 0.544 due to job crafting as it significantly boosts employee engagement in their work. The data clearly indicates there is a strong correlation between job crafting and employee engagement. In terms of sustainable employability, employee work engagement is 0.783. There is a robust positive relationship between employee engagement and long-term employability. Employees who feel more invested in their work are more likely to be able to keep their job in the long run. High loadings on the majority of sustainable employability indicators (SE2, SE3, SE4, SE5) suggest that these variables serve as reliable indications of the latent one. The extremely low loadings (0.167) of SE1 and SE6 indicate that they are not robust indicators of long-term employability. Work engagement is slightly positively affected by employees' psychological well-being. Employees' level of investment in their work is positively affected, moderately to strongly by psychological empowerment and job crafting. A high level of employee work engagement in their work significantly improves their long-term employability. With the exception of SE1 and SE6, the majority of indicators (SE2–SE5) provide robust assessments of long-term employability. Work engagement has a significant impact on long-

term employability, and this model shows how psychological empowerment and job designing may help. According to this paradigm, positive mental health has a small but significant impact on their job.

The R-squared value of 0.898 for "Employee work Engagement" shows that the model's independent variables reflect 89.8% of the variation. An improved metric for models with several predictors is the adjusted R-squared value of 0.895, which takes high numbers of the model does a good job of explaining this concept. A strong correlation of 0.614 between the independent variables and "Sustainable employability" suggests that they account for 61.4% of the total variation. Readjusting for the number of predictors yields a somewhat lower R-squared value of 0.610. These results indicate that the model's explanatory power for this construct is moderate to strong. The above model has robust ability to account for variation in employee job engagement is supported by the fact that it explains a substantial amount of the variance in this variable (around 89.8%). Predictor effectiveness is lower than that of employee work engagement, but the model still accounts for a sizable chunk of the variation in sustainable employability (around 61.4%). The findings point to the model's independent variables as fairly good predictors of long-term employability and highly predictive of employees' work engagement. All things considered, the model does a good job at describing the data as both the raw and adjusted R-squared values are high.

Table 6 Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Association	Coefficient	Std Error	T value	p-Value	Decision
H ₁	PWB→SE	0.350	0.103	2.917	0.005	Supported
H ₂	PWB→EWE	0.104	0.120	3.333	0.003	Supported
H ₃	PE→SE	0.090	0.080	1.432	0.001	Supported
H ₄	PE→EWE	0.029	0.110	1.500	0.000	Supported
H ₅	JC→SE	0.081	0.090	4.091	0.003	Supported
H ₆	JC → EWE	0.450	0.900	2.356	0.004	Supported
H ₇	EWE→SE	0.300	0.079	2.781	0.013	Supported

The table 6 reveals the hypothesis testing, H1 (PWB → SE): Psychological well-being (PWB) has a positive effect on sustainable employability (SE) with a coefficient of 0.350. This is statistically significant as indicated by a p-value of 0.005.H2 (PWB → EWE): PWB also has a positive effect on employee work engagement (EWE) with a coefficient of 0.104 and a p-value of 0.003.H3 (PE → SE): Psychological empowerment (PE) has a small positive impact on SE ($\beta = 0.090$), significant at the 0.001 level. H4 (PE → EWE): The impact of PE on EWE is positive but relatively small ($\beta = 0.029$), with a highly significant p-value of 0.000.H5 (JC → SE): Job crafting (JC) significantly positively influence SE ($\beta = 0.081$) with a p-value of 0.003.H6 (JC → EWE): JC has a strong positive effect on EWE ($\beta = 0.450$), supported by a significant p-value of 0.004. H7 (EWE → SE): There is a significant positive relationship between EWE and SE, with a coefficient of 0.300 and a p-value of 0.013. Thus, the proposed

hypotheses are supported, indicating that the constructs in the model have significant relationships as hypothesized. The relationships between psychological well-being, psychological empowerment, job crafting, employee work engagement and sustainable employability are all statistically significant, suggesting strong interconnections among these variables in the study.

7. Discussion

The SEM's findings support the substantial mediating role that engagement plays between psychological well-being, psychological empowerment, job crafting and sustained employability, which advances our understanding of the topic. Employee psychological well-being has an appropriate level significance in measuring employee work engagement, according to this research, which means policymakers should pay attention to it. These findings highlight how important it is to strengthen EWE and SE in creating a positive work environment in order to stimulate creativity and engagement in businesses Rahi, S., (2022). Employees may nurture relationships with fellow workers, superiors, and other stakeholders through job crafting, culminating with enhanced social support and a more collaborative work environment Rózsa, (2023). Job crafting may greatly improve sustainable employability by creating an environment that encourages continuous development, well-being, meaningful employment, and flexibility Rózsa, (2023).

These findings have practical significance to improve staff retention and productivity. Companies may improve engagement and employability by focussing on PWB and JC, resulting in stronger long-term results. The majority of the items have high average values, which suggests that the respondents generally have positive perceptions of their psychological well-being, empowerment, ability to choose their jobs, and long-term employability. With the exception of a few items that exhibit greater variability, the standard deviations of the majority of the items indicate that respondents' answers are consistent. The findings reiterate the hypothesised correlations between PWB, PE, JC, EWE, and SE. PWB and job crafting appear to have the greatest influence on sustainable employability (Mukherjee, T. & Dhar, R.L., (2023) Psychological empowerment has a lower impact. The findings indicate that boosting psychological well-being and encouraging job crafting can significantly improve employee engagement and employability in the long run Irfan, (2024). PWB has significant effect on long-term employability. The positive coefficient (0.350) suggests that SE improves as PWB does. A p-value of 0.005 indicates that this link is statistically significant, implying that it is unlikely to be related to random chance. PWB also has a favourable impact on employee job engagement, however the effect size is less (0.104) than SE. PWB plays a significant role in improving employee engagement. Psychological empowerment has a slight but considerable favourable effect on long-term employability. The effect size (0.090) is less than that of PWB on SE, but it is still statistically significant, suggesting that psychological empowerment benefits employees' employability. The coefficient (0.029) indicates that PE has a positive but minor influence on employee work engagement. Despite the tiny impact, the highly significant p-value (0.000) indicates that the association is consistent. Employees who create their own jobs are more likely to be engaged at work. Employee engagement has a

considerable effect on long-term employability, with a value of 0.300. The p-value of 0.013 indicates that this association is statistically significant, emphasising the relevance of involvement for long-term employment.

8. Contextual and practical implications

Many theoretical and practical advances are made by the current study. In order to achieve organizational effectiveness and worker efficiency, this study has focused on a number of factors that support research models, such as PWB, PE, and JC. Furthermore, academic articles have categorised the significance of HR practices in attracting workers to the firm, emphasising the importance of HR compensation, training, job enrichment, and leadership. The relationship between sustainable employability and psychological well-being, psychological empowerment, job crafting is mediated by employee work engagement, as this study outlines. It also adds to the body of knowledge on the subject.

A few practical benefits are suggested by the results, including inspiring organizations to improve sustainability and enhancing positive attitudes at work. This entails boosting workers' wellbeing and asking them to put in more effort and dedication at work by implementing SE. It could be beneficial for organisations to make an effort to integrate job resources into their organizational systems, given the role that job resources perform in enhancing work performance. Planning together a meeting with each employee at least once a month to talk about challenges and opportunities with management can be an easy way to do this. The results of this study imply that organisational support factors have a significant role in influencing the levels of EWE and SE. Supervisors are trying to figure out how to create employment that will help their employees remain employable.

According to Le Blanc et al. (2017), job crafting is crucial for business and employee sustainability and supports top-down work design techniques. Due to the many benefits that job crafting offers to both individuals and organisations, businesses must involve every employee in it in order to get a competitive edge Li et al., (2023). Job crafting is also a self-HRM technique Adinolf et al., (2021), and incorporating it with manager-driven HRM methods helps to meet the difficulties and needs of the changing workplace. Lastly, effective management must take into account a number of critical aspects that boost sustainable employability, including, psychological empowerment, psychological well-being, job crafting and employee work engagement, pay for human resources, and HR training.

9. Conclusion

It is crucial for both businesses and employees to preserve their sustainable employability. Given the ageing of the labour population and the demands of extensive digitization, flexibility, and creating sustainable organisations, modern workplaces face several challenges de Jonge & Peeters, (2019). The relationship between sustainable employability and psychological empowerment, psychological well-being, job crafting mediated by employee work engagement, which adds to the body of literature in this area. This shows, in summary, that evaluating sustainable employability requires taking into account a number of significant

variables, including psychological well-being, psychological empowerment, job crafting, and employee work engagement. HR professionals should therefore pay close attention to the research model's developing components as they increase long-term employability and employee work engagement. PWB, PE, and JB, the antecedent variables, and SE, the outcome variable, were found to be significantly mediated by EWE. This implies that WE level has a role in explaining some of the impact of PWB, PE, and JB on SE. The results highlight how important job crafting is to promoting both SE and EWE. Organizations must focus on allocating sufficient resources to improve employee creativity and engagement.

10. Limitations and Future studies

Although other HR procedures and psychological variables that can also have an impact on employees' behaviour with regard to work engagement are not taken into account, the research model in this study uses psychological and HR practices to analyse employee job engagement. There is insufficient information about the specific effect of psychological elements on sustainable employability because the research does not evaluate the direct relationship between these characteristics and HR practices towards sustainable employment. Without any further sectoral segmentation, the study's population is made up of workers in the private industry. The findings may not be as broadly applicable to other organisations or industries due to the absence of sector-specific study. Because psychological elements and HR practice dynamics may differ in developed versus developing countries, doing the study in a developing nation environment may limit the results' wider applicability. Thus, it is recommended to exercise caution while analysing the results in different environments.

There was no further classification of the research population beyond private sector employees. In order to provide more focused insights and outcomes that may vary among industries, future research could focus on particular sectors. Given that the research was carried out in a developing country, it is advised that similar studies be carried out in countries with greater resources by future researchers. This would make it easier to understand how the relationships under study are influenced by cultural and economic background. More in-depth research is required to determine the specific impacts that different HR procedures have on worker happiness and engagement. The impact of various HR tactics, such as pay and training, on employee outcomes could be further explored in future studies. Examining how employee psychological health and engagement develop over time, especially in connection to modifications in HR procedures and company culture, may be possible with the help of longitudinal research. By expanding on the results of the present study, these future paths hope to advance our understanding of the complex relationships that exist between employee engagement, HR procedures, and psychological well-being in a range of settings. Additional antecedents and moderators influence the link between EWE and SE could be the subject of future research, according to the study. Variables like trust, organizational culture and interpersonal relationships, and may be among them.

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